

TRAINING STRATEGY TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF AN INTELLIGENT DETECTION SYSTEM*

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Detection systems of computer accesses are essential for information security. In this article we propose a classification system that combines two intelligent algorithms: Supervised Classification Systems, UCS, and Decision Trees, C4.5. The experiments were carried out using a dataset provided by Amazon, the Kaggle challenge. The system has been trained by dividing the dataset into subgroup. This training strategy has resulted more efficient than if the whole database is used as an only set. Results prove that the use of the proposed detection system provides higher classification accuracy and reduces the percentage of false positives in comparison to other classification techniques.

1. Introduction

The security problem of data loss in information systems is important and concerns public and private companies worldwide[1]. This problem occurs when employees make incorrect use of the access to a resource because they steal confidential information or perform operations they are not allowed to.

The leakage of confidential information is one of the greatest threats for any country. It is necessary to develop efficiency methods to prevent these attacks

* This work has been partially supported by Government of the Republic of Ecuador.

[2, 3]. But the problem is complex because it involves the creation of a behavioral profile of each employee, and this profile changes dynamically. Furthermore, it can be uncertain at some stages. Therefore the application of intelligent techniques has been proved to be very useful for dealing with these problems[4].

Some of the most used methods for dealing with this problem are classification techniques[5]. Although there are many intrusion detection systems, it is still an open issue because the number of false positives when detecting fraud is usually high. The detection system proposed in this paper is based on two classification methodologies: Decision Trees (C4.5) [6], and Supervised Classification Systems (UCS) [7]. It has resulted more accurate than their application separately.

Moreover, to improve the efficiency of this detection system, this work proposes a learning strategy that consists of dividing the training set into subgroups. These subgroups are formed according to some attributes that provide relevant information for the classification.

The database used for testing this proposal is the Amazon dataset Kaggle Challenge, which contains accesses of employees of that company during the period of 2010 and 2011. The data consists of real, historical data [8]. Users were allowed or denied access to the different system resources manually.

The goal of this work is to generate an automatic method that analyzes the data in order to predict the rejection or acceptance of the accesses to the system resources by an employee.

2. Materials and Methods

Figure 1 shows the process followed for the classification of accesses to the computer system resources. The process initiates with the information about the users' accesses that is pre-processed (discretization, normalization). Then, the now refined datasets are divided into groups according to some relevant attributes. This is done by using filters and wrappers. The classifier is generated by combining decision trees C4.5 Supervised Classification Systems. This classifier is applied to each of the groups of the dataset. Finally an error function has been defined to evaluate and validate the classifier.

Figure 1. Accesses Classifier System.

2.1. Dataset Kaggle Amazon

The data consists of real, historical data collected in 2010 and 2011. The employees were allowed or denied access manually. We have used 32,769 records for training and 58,921 for tests. The operations are described by 10 attributes such as: time (day, hour), action (allowed, 0, or denied, 1), resource (file accessed), role of the user, department, etc.

The pre-processing consists of eliminating redundancy, noise, etc. using filters and wrappers [9].

3. Generation of an Intelligent Detection System

The intelligent detection system has been generating combining Decision Trees C4.5, and Supervised Classification System UCS, which uses genetic algorithms to create classification rules. These techniques were selected after applying several ones because these gave the best results with the dataset of Amazon.

3.1. Division of Data for Training

First of all, in order to eliminate redundancy and noise, the analysis tool Wakaito Environment for Knowledge Analysis (WEKA) [10] was used. Then the dataset was divided regarding the most relevant attributes.

To find the correlation between the attributes we applied a wrapper [11]. After that, the Gain Ranking Filter showed that the most significant one in terms of discrimination was resource. That is, the resource the user accesses is the attribute that most influence on the final value the attribute Action (denied or allowed access).

Therefore, the registers that correspond to allowed accesses were sorted out in descending order according to the resource. They were divided into 15 groups. All the denied accesses were added to each group (Figure 2).

RESOURCE	MGR_ID	ROLE_ROLLUP_1	ROLE_ROLLUP_2	ROLE_DEPTNAME	ROLE_FAMILY_DESC	ROLE_TITLE	ROLE_CODE	ROLE_FAMILY	ACTION
13878	54258	117890	118102	117878	117879	117905	117880	290919	0
19723	54762	117951	117952	118008	117879	118536	117880	308574	0
20284	60823	118953	118954	117941	117886	117879	117880	19721	0
27416	50601	117916	117917	117941	117886	118321	117880	290919	0
36646	27873	117978	117979	117884	117886	119323	117880	19793	0
37732	65460	118079	118080	117878	118177	118568	117880	19721	0
37734	119058	118079	118080	117878	118177	118980	117880	118295	0
38480	51382	118079	118080	117878	118177	126820	117880	118638	0
42085	59000	118181	118182	117941	117897	128230	117880	4673	0
64721	50589	118079	118080	117878	121386	117879	117880	19721	0
3853	20560	117876	117877	117878	117879	118784	117880	290919	1
20279	17695	117890	117891	117878	117879	119093	117880	119095	1
25330	19702	118269	118270	117878	117879	120773	117880	118960	1
33642	13196	117951	117952	117941	117897	119962	117880	118205	1
36674	14633	118106	118107	117884	117886	118321	117880	290919	1
78766	56683	118079	118080	117878	304519	117885	117880	117887	1
79228	13400	117983	117984	117878	117879	118321	117880	290919	1
81480	96704	117910	117911	117884	117886	128230	117880	118704	1

Access Denied, Allowed Access

Figure 2. Division of Amazon dataset into sub groups.

3.2. Selection of the Classification Techniques

Once the dataset is divided into sub groups, different classification techniques are applied to this data and evaluated. Table 2 summarizes the performance on each of the methodologies that have been tried on the Amazon dataset. The best results are reached with the decision trees C4.5 and the UCS, which give a percentage of right classification of 98.3 % and 97.6 %, respectively.

Table 2. Classification Techniques Accuracy for each of the subgroups of the dataset.

DATASET	ACCURACY						
	ID3	XCS	BAYES Net	RNM	C4.5	UCS	SVM
D1	0.970	0.950	0.969	0.974	0.982	0.981	0.950
D2	0.978	0.945	0.981	0.952	0.988	0.981	0.927
D3	0.994	0.956	0.992	0.972	0.997	0.994	0.920
D4	0.976	0.869	0.961	0.972	0.985	0.981	0.896
D5	0.963	0.912	0.928	0.948	0.973	0.967	0.780
D6	0.969	0.951	0.974	0.973	0.983	0.974	0.765
D7	0.967	0.950	0.965	0.939	0.976	0.973	0.691
D8	0.976	0.913	0.921	0.890	0.990	0.974	0.784
D9	0.968	0.886	0.975	0.923	0.982	0.975	0.797
D10	0.976	0.838	0.975	0.901	0.982	0.974	0.795
D11	0.963	0.910	0.964	0.922	0.971	0.973	0.884
D12	0.982	0.897	0.984	0.924	0.990	0.977	0.884
D13	0.975	0.972	0.956	0.924	0.979	0.972	0.654
D14	0.967	0.944	0.979	0.926	0.983	0.977	0.654
D15	0.973	0.927	0.978	0.926	0.981	0.976	0.654
AVERAGE	0.973	0.921	0.967	0.938	0.983	0.976	0.802

3.3. Generating the Detection System

The detection system combines the outputs of the classifiers C4.5 and UCS. But then the results given for each of these techniques is weighted and introduced in

a rule base system. Figure 3 shows the model of the final classifier and its respective tools and modules.

Figure 3. Design of the intelligent detection system.

The final detection system applies a rule given by (1) to weight the answers obtained by the two classification techniques over each subgroup, being R1 the tree C4.5 and R2 the UCS. Different weights were tried but these ones give the best results. They are related to the efficiency of each technique.

$$Result = \frac{3R1}{5} + \frac{2R2}{5} \tag{1}$$

4. Experiment Results

The detection system was applied to the Amazon dataset. The results prove an accuracy of 0.984 in training and 0.981 in the tests. The KEEL (Knowledge Extraction bases on Evolutionary Learning) [12] tool for training and testing classification techniques are used. Table 3 shows the percentage of hits in comparison to other techniques.

Table 3. Comparison of the classification algorithms with the dataset Amazon.

ALGORITHM	ACCURACY	
	TRAIN	TEST
Meta Classifier System UCS and C4.5	0.984	0.981
Naive Bayes	0.912	0.901
UCS	0.949	0.939
XCS	0.942	0.936
Multilayer perceptron	0.942	0.94
J48	0.945	0.941

5. Conclusions

In this paper we have proposed an intelligent decision system that allows us to detect intrusions in information systems.

This intelligent classifier combines some techniques, in our case, decision trees and UCS, as it has been proved that the fusion of these strategies improves the accuracy of the classifier in comparison to the application of different techniques but separately.

On the other hand, in order to train the system we have divided the data set into subgroups, regarding some relevant attribute. Then we have added all the cases of intrusions in each group. This strategy improves the efficiency of the classifier.

Simulation results show how the system reaches a high percentage of hits in the classification of accesses.

Future work includes obtaining a dynamic profile of the behaviour of the user. Furthermore, this profile should change in an adaptive way with the performance of the users.

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